

THE ROLE OF ERROR AND ERROR CORRECTION IN EFL TEACHING.

Fazliddinova Zulfiyakhon Dilmurod qizi
English filology faculty, Namangan state university.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7061477>

Abstract

As everyone learn anything they make mistakes and errors by doing that they improve their skills. Making errors is considered as an essential part of learning in EFL classes. However not each student comprehends the teachers feedback positively , so how teachers should correct students errors in the case when students do not understand their mistakes and often students repeat one error several times, which irritates teaches most. Teachers' and students' beliefs in this sphere is controversial. This review of articles tries to answer those questions and encourage teachers and students to use their errors in English language learning in a

Keywords: English language learning, error, error correction, feedback, teachers' beliefs, students' beliefs.

Introduction

English language has become one of the most used language so that many students learn this language nowadays. However while learning process, they face a great deal of mistakes and this irritates them from studying. Teachers also have the problems of how to give positive feedback and correct students' error as students psychology differs they find challenging to approach them in positive ways.

Providing feedback and correcting students errors has been always a challenging issue for teachers. If students make errors it means that they are learning and this can be an useful clue for teachers to find out the missing knowledge of students to correct them. Inappropriate feedback or correction of students' mistakes can be negative and harmful in some cases.

According to Gumbaridze (2012) following factors are the reason why students make errors in learning process:

1. Transferring grammatical, phonetical and lexical features from L1 to L2 or to English as foreign language.
2. In difficultness of the learning language especially, in the use of polysemantic words, omonyms, phrasal verbs and use of idioms.
3. Overgeneralization can be next factor for example misuse of comparative and superlative forms of adjectives and adverbs.
4. Fossilization , as students faulty effects to their psychology and if they repeatedly make mistakes they feel that they cannot correct their errors.
5. Lack of speaking or communicative process.
6. Fatigue and carelessness
7. Feeling inferiority and low self- esteem.
8. Inhibition
9. The shortage of empathy between teachers and students.

To correct students' error and encourage their study mostly teachers utilize next techniques:

1. Echoing
2. Repetition up the correct answer
3. Prompting
4. Making notes of common mistakes
5. Nonverbal way
6. Reformulation
7. Recording on tape.

Many teachers believe that error correction gives positive results and Zhu to find out their opinion about error correction did a survey and according to that survey teacher correction(63.3) is mostly preferred technique and peer correction(16,7) were leading techniques.

Theoretical framework

Everyone learns from the errors they make in their life. Making mistakes is crucial as if a student is doing error it means that he is learning the language. The significance of error in language learning was firstly explored by Corder in 1967 and Selinker continued Corder's theories in this field (Amara, 2015). Error is the misuse and incorrect utilization of grammatical structures, language competences, pronunciation errors, phonetic errors and so on. According to Amara (2015) native speakers can correct their mistakes faster than EFL speakers as they know their mother languages grammatical and linguistic, pragmatic and phonologic competences better than EFL speakers. So we can conclude that students may commit an error if they do not know or do not understand the language competences.

It is difficult to correct the errors by students as they have several in misunderstanding of each language has its own structures and they often mix foreign language grammar with their L1.

First error, is called as language transfer and interlingual interference.(Amara,2015) these errors are the results of the mixture of two or more languages. The same error shows Gumbardze (2012) and his list of errors are the following;

1. Transferring grammatical, phonetical and lexical features from L1 to L2 or to English as foreign language.
2. In difficultness of the learning language especially, in the use of polysemantic words, omonyms, phrasal verbs and use of idioms.
3. Overgeneralization can be next factor for example misuse of comparative and superlative forms of adjectives and adverbs.
4. Fossilization, as students faulty effects to their psychology and if they repeatedly make mistakes they feel that they cannot correct their errors.
5. Lack of speaking or communicative process.
6. Fatigue and carelessness
7. Feeling inferiority and low self- esteem.
8. Inhibition
9. The shortage of empathy between teachers and students.

Teachers' attitude to errors; it is said that teachers are afraid of the students' error and always try to do not mistakes during the class they think that if a teacher makes mistake each

student repeats it and they cannot correct that error and teachers believe that committing errors are very harmful however errors mistakes are the part of each one's life.

To treat error teachers should answer several questions and use mostly used techniques and be active in learning and exploring students' errors and theories that are recommended by scientists. Next questions firstly should be answered and then I provide some techniques to utilize during the process;

Henrickson (1987 cited in Amara 2015) provides five fundamental questions for teachers;

- 1) Should I correct error
- 2) When to correct the error
- 3) Whose error to correct
- 4) How should I correct the error individually or in class
- 5) Should I correct or give chance for the student to find and correct his /her error.

To correct students' error and encourage their study mostly teachers utilize next techniques:

1. Echoing
2. Repetition up the correct answer
3. Prompting
4. Making notes of common mistakes
5. Nonverbal way
6. Reformulation
7. Recording on tape.

Zhu (2010) recommends some techniques to eliminate error problems;

1. Consider students preferences; as soon as teacher know how to approach students it becomes easier to correct the students without misunderstandings.
2. When and how to correct; teacher must differentiate error and mistake. Mistakes can be self corrected and errors should be corrected by teachers guide.
3. Promoting and teaching students self-correction techniques ; giving students chance to correct their own error gives amazing result as students and find out where and how they make a mistake and they understand how the structures or other competences work.
4. Encourage peer correction; students work better in groups and students understand each other better as their intuitions are the same so they may help each other not to repeat the error.
5. Feedback; using a wide range of feedbacks can help students as they understand their error and try to correct them there are several types of feedback mostly preferred are usually, explicit correction, recast, clarification, elicitation and repetition.

Amara studied the error that are made by undergraduates of Algeria and most influences factor in making errors was the effects of the mother tongue(2015). Zhu studied the preference on correction methods and according to the study 63.3 % students preferred teacher correction, 16.7% students prefer peer correction and 20 5 of students try to correct themselves (2010). Furthermore other studies done by Gumbaridze, 2012; Diab, 2005; 2006; Hamouda, 2011; Abedi, Latifi et. Al., 2010; Geiller ,2014; Swain, 1988 and et.al also prove that error correction is an essential part in English language learning.

Conclusion

All in all, error and mistake are different conceptions and error should be corrected by the help of teachers. Teachers also have difficulties in correction methods of errors and to effectively use and encourage their students not to make error that should keep an eye with

theories in this field. By utilizing teacher correction, peer correction and self correction methodologies students can learn the language while committing errors. However errors are considered to be pertinent part of learning English language.

References:

1. Luc Geiller, 2014, How EFL students can use Google to correct their 'untreatable' written errors, the EUROCALL review, vol 22, no.2, 26-45 pages.
2. Merrill Swain, 1988, Manipulating and complementing content teaching to Maximize Second language learning, tesl Canada Journal, vol 6, no. 1 68-83 pages.
3. Razie Abedi, Mehdi Latifi, Ahmad Moinzadeh, 2010, The effect of error correction vs. error detection on Iranian pre-intermediate Efl learners' writing achievements, English language teaching, vol 3, no. 4 168-174 pages.
4. Arafat Hamouda, 2011, A study of students and teachers' preferences and attitudes towards correction of classroom written errors in Saudi EFL context, English language teaching , Vol 4, no.4 128-141 pages.
5. Rula Diab, 2006 , error correction and feedback in the EFL writing classroom, English teaching forum, no. 3 2-14 pages.
6. Jujuna Gumbaridze, 2012, Error correction in EFL speaking classrooms, Procedia-social and behavioral sciences, 70 92003) 1660-1663
7. Fang, Xue-mei, 2007, Error analysis and the EFL classroom teaching, US-China review, vol.4, no. 4 10-14 pages
8. Honglin Zhu, 2010, An analysis of college students' attitudes towards error correction in EFL context, English language teaching , Vol 3, no.4 127-131 pages.
9. Naimi Amara, 2015, Errors correction in Foreign language teaching, The online journal of new Horizons in education, vol 5, issue 3, 58-68 pages.
10. Rula L Diab, 2001 Efl university students' preferences for error correction and teacher feedback on writing, TESL reporter 38, 1 (2005) pp. 27-51.